

Clinico-Epidemiological Study of Poisoning – A Descriptive Study

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Received: 11 May 2026
Accepted: 18 May 2026
Published Online: 5 June 2026

Published by:
Gopalganj Medical College, Gopalganj,
Bangladesh

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DOI:

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ABSTRACT

Background: Acute poisoning is a major public health and clinical emergency in Bangladesh, yet prospective data characterizing its epidemiological pattern, clinical presentation and outcomes at a tertiary level remain limited. **Objective:** To describe the clinico-epidemiological profile, pattern of poisoning agents and immediate outcomes of acute poisoning cases admitted to Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH). **Methods & Materials:** A prospective observational study was conducted in two medicine units of DMCH from July to December 2010. A total of 600 consenting adult poisoning patients were enrolled after applying predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data on demographic profile, poisoning agent, clinical features, investigations, treatment and outcome were recorded on a structured case record form. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 17.0. **Results:** Poisoning accounted for 21.45% of hospital admissions. The majority of patients were aged 21–30 years (43.3%), with a male predominance (60.2%). Pesticides (29.2%) were the most common agents, followed by travel-related poisoning (27.3%) and benzodiazepines (20.2%). Suicidal intent was present in 66.2% of cases. Common clinical features included nausea/vomiting (62.7%) and drowsiness (55.7%). Most patients (73.3%) recovered, while 3% died. Mortality was highest among pesticide poisoning cases. Lower Glasgow Coma Scale scores on admission were strongly associated with increased mortality. **Conclusion:** Acute poisoning predominantly affects young adults, with pesticide and travel-related poisoning as the dominant agents. Lower GCS on admission is a significant predictor of mortality. Strengthening public awareness, legislative control of toxic agrochemicals and improved emergency care infrastructure are urgently needed.

Keywords: acute poisoning; epidemiology; pesticide; Glasgow Coma Scale, Bangladesh

(The Insight 2026; 9(2): 333-339)

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INTRODUCTION

Poisoning is a common medico-social problem that has drawn worldwide attention owing to the growing incidence of accidental or intentional exposure to chemicals in industrial, agricultural and domestic settings. Abuse and overuse of pharmaceutical agents have further compounded the hazards of poisoning and the consequent burden of morbidity and mortality is substantial [1].

Globally, poisoning constitutes a significant public health concern. According to World Health Organization (WHO) data from 2004, an estimated 346,000 people died worldwide from unintentional poisoning, of whom 91% were from low- and middle-income countries. In the same year, unintentional poisoning caused the loss of over 7.4 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). Deliberate ingestion of pesticides alone is estimated to cause approximately 370,000 deaths annually, a figure that could be substantially reduced through restrictive regulation of highly toxic agrochemicals [2]. Snake bite, similarly, constitutes a largely neglected public health challenge, with an estimated five million bites, up to 2.5 million envenoming's and at least 100,000 deaths occurring each year worldwide [2].

Across different regions, the pattern of poisoning is shaped by socioeconomic context, prevailing agricultural practices and access to pharmaceuticals. In the United Kingdom, acute poisoning accounts for 10 to 20% of all acute medical

admissions, with paracetamol implicated in nearly 48% of overdoses [3,4]. In South and South-East Asia, pesticide ingestion is endemic and constitutes the leading cause of poisoning death, with case fatality rates for self-poisoning ranging from 10 to 20% in developing countries, compared with 0.5 to 1% in industrialized nations [4]. In the United States, approximately five million poison exposures occur each year, predominantly acute and accidental, with pharmaceuticals involved in 47% of exposures and 84% of serious or fatal cases [5].

In Bangladesh, poisoning causes an estimated 16,000 episodes and 1,500 deaths per year [6]. The epidemiological pattern has shifted over recent decades, moving from endrin and organophosphorus compound-related suicidal poisoning towards benzodiazepine-based travel-related (transport) poisoning, an emerging socio-legal phenomenon in which travellers are stupefied and robbed [7,8]. According to the Bangladesh Health Bulletin of 2010, poisoning was the fifth most common cause of hospital admission and the third leading cause of death in upazila health complexes. In the economically active age groups of 15 to 24 and 25 to 49 years, poisoning was the leading cause of in-patient mortality across multiple tiers of government health facilities [9].

The epidemiological profile of poisoning in Bangladesh is distinct from that of Western countries, given the differing social structure, economic status, educational level, awareness

and availability of toxic agents [10,11]. Many countries operate established Poison Control Centers, but this important public health infrastructure remains underdeveloped in Bangladesh [10]. Identification of high-risk circumstances, susceptible population subgroups, chemical substances and commercial products involved in poisoning can meaningfully guide preventive strategies and improve clinical management [12]. Despite the scale of the problem, prospective hospital-based data on the clinico-epidemiological characteristics of acute poisoning in Bangladesh are limited. Studies from tertiary centers provide a representative cross-section of severe cases and can document emerging trends in poisoning agents, demographic vulnerability, clinical presentation and outcomes. The present study was therefore conducted to describe the clinical symptomatology, epidemiological profile and immediate outcome of acute poisoning cases admitted to a major teaching hospital in Dhaka, with the expectation that the findings would inform clinical practice, public health policy and future preventive interventions.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study was to describe the clinico-epidemiological profile, pattern of poisoning agents and immediate outcomes of acute poisoning cases admitted to Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH).

METHODS & MATERIALS

This was a prospective observational study conducted in two adult medicine inpatient units (Unit 5 and Unit 10) of Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH), Dhaka, Bangladesh. DMCH is one of the largest and busiest tertiary teaching hospitals in the country, receiving patients from Dhaka city and the surrounding districts. The study was carried out over a period of six months, from 1st July 2010 to 31st December 2010. During this period, all poisoning cases presenting through the emergency department and admitted to the two study units were evaluated. A total of 2,890 patients were admitted to the study units over this period, of whom 620 (21.45%) were poisoning cases. After excluding 20 cases that did not provide informed consent, 600 patients were enrolled as the final study population.

Selection Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- All adult patients (aged 13 years and above) admitted to Medicine Units 5 and 10 of DMCH through the emergency department following confirmed or suspected poisoning were eligible for inclusion.
- Patients with a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score ranging from 3 to 15 at the time of admission were included.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Any other organic cause of coma or altered consciousness was identified through history, clinical examination, or investigations, including complete blood count, random blood sugar, liver function tests, renal function tests, serum electrolytes, or other relevant tests.
- The patient or their attendant was unwilling to provide informed written consent for participation in the study.

Data Collection Procedure

Patients admitted as suspected poisoning cases were initially screened by the study physician. Enrolment was cross-checked against the nurses' Patient Register and Admission Book to ensure completeness. After applying the exclusion criteria, a detailed history and systematic clinical examination were performed for all enrolled participants. Diagnosis was established based on the patient's own account, the statement of any accompanying witness, the odour of the toxic substance, any physical specimens brought by attendants and the characteristic clinical syndrome clusters observed at presentation. Where the poison container was available, the generic name, quantity, colour and smell were documented. Relevant investigations, including complete blood count, random blood sugar, serum glutamic-pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), serum bilirubin, prothrombin time, blood urea, serum creatinine, serum electrolytes and chest radiography, were carried out to exclude alternative diagnoses and to assess severity or complications. In the emergency department, gastric lavage was performed when clinically indicated before admission to the ward. All patients were assessed for vital signs on arrival and managed accordingly. Subsequent clinical management was directed by the consultant physician of the respective unit and tailored to the type, estimated amount, route and time elapsed since poisoning. Daily follow-up was maintained until recovery and discharge or death. Clinical recovery was defined as the patient becoming fully conscious with stable vital signs. Patients requiring assisted ventilation were referred to the intensive care unit (ICU); however, where ICU beds were unavailable, patients were intubated in the ward and transferred as soon as a bed became available. Outcomes were categorized as: discharge with advice (recovered), discharge on risk bond (DORB), absconded (left against medical advice), or death. Cause of death was documented through death summaries. Psychiatric evaluation was performed by a psychiatrist from the Mental Health Department of DMCH for all cases of deliberate self-harm. Data were recorded systematically on a structured Case Record Form (CRF).

Ethical Considerations

All enrolled patients or their attendants were informed about the nature, purpose and procedures of the study in their local language using a printed information sheet. Participation was entirely voluntary and the right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence was clearly communicated. Confidentiality of all patient information was strictly maintained throughout the study. Informed written consent was obtained from each patient or their legal attendant before enrolment. The study protocol was reviewed and ethical clearance was granted by the Ethical Review Committee of Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Statistical Analysis

All data were entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics software, version 17.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). A detailed multi-variable database was constructed for the study population. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for all categorical variables. Continuous variables were described using the mean and range. Associations between categorical variables, including sex and intention of poisoning, sex and poisoning agent and GCS score and clinical outcome, were assessed using the chi-square test. Student's t-test was applied where comparison of means was required. A p-value of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

RESULTS

Table I shows the Hospital Admission Profile, Length of Stay and Demographic Characteristics of Fatal Poisoning Cases. During the six-month study period, a total of 2,890 patients were admitted to the two study medicine units of DMCH, of whom 243 (8.40%) died from all causes. Of all admitted patients, 620 (21.45%) were poisoning cases; 20 of these did not provide consent and were excluded, leaving 600 patients

in the study cohort. Eighteen (3.0%) of the 600 study patients died due to poisoning. The mean duration of hospital stay across all poisoning patients was 2.81 days; 399 (66.5%) patients stayed 1 to 3 days, 158 (26.3%) stayed 4 to 6 days and 43 (7.2%) required more than six days of admission. Among the 18 fatal cases, the majority (15 cases, 83.3%) were between 21 and 40 years of age and male patients predominated (12 cases, 65.6%).

Table I: Hospital Admission Profile, Length of Stay and Demographic Characteristics of Fatal Poisoning Cases

Variable / Category	Number (n)	Percentage (%)	
Hospital admission profile (n=2890)	Total patients admitted	2890	
	Total deaths (all causes)	243	8.4
	Total poisoning cases	620	21.45
	Study cohort (consenting patients)	600	—
	Deaths due to poisoning (study cohort)	18	3
Duration of hospital stay (n=600)	1-3 days	399	66.5
	4-6 days	158	26.3
	>6 days	43	7.2
	Mean hospital stay (days)	2.81	—
Age group of fatal cases (n=18)	<20 years	1	5.5
	21-30 years	10	55
	31-40 years	5	27.7
	41-50 years	1	5.5
	>50 years	1	5.5
Gender distribution of fatal cases (n=18)	Male	12	65.6
	Female	6	33.3

The socio-demographic profile of the 600 study patients is presented in Table II. Poisoning was predominantly a disorder of younger individuals. Most patients were 30 years of age or younger (26.5% were aged 20 years or below and 43.3% were in the 21 to 30-year age group), with incidence declining progressively with advancing age. The mean age was 28.29 years, with a range of 13 to 80 years. Male patients (361, 60.2%) outnumbered female patients (239, 39.8%), giving a male-to-female ratio of approximately 3:2. Educational

attainment was moderate, with the majority completing high school (37.2%) or intermediate level (31.6%) education. Students constituted the largest occupational group (181, 31.1%), followed by housewives (147, 24.5%) and service workers (133, 22.1%). The majority of patients were Muslim (553, 92.2%), reflecting the national demographic composition. Married patients (320, 53.3%) slightly outnumbered unmarried patients (269, 44.8%). Most patients (457, 76.2%) were from urban areas.

Table II: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Poisoning Cases (n=600)

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Number (n)	Percentage (%)	
Age group (years)	≤20	159	26.5
	21-30	260	43.3
	31-40	113	18.8
	41-50	42	7.0
	>50	26	4.3
	Mean age	28.29 years	
Sex	Male	361	60.2
	Female	239	39.8
Educational level	Illiterate	46	7.6
	Primary	111	18.5
	High school	223	37.2
	Intermediate	190	31.6
	Graduate and above	30	5.0
Occupation	Student	181	31.1
	Housewife	147	24.5
	Service	133	22.1
	Businessman	77	12.8
	Farmer	42	7.0
	Others	20	3.3
Marrital status	Married	320	53.3
	Unmarried	269	44.8
	Other (separated/divorced/widow)	11	1.8
Residence	Urban	457	76.2
	Rural	143	23.8

Figure 1. Distribution of Poisoning Agents among Study Patients (n=600)

The distribution of poisoning agents is illustrated in *Figure 1*. Pesticide was the most commonly used poisoning agent, recorded in 175 (29.2%) patients, followed by travel-related (stupefying) poisoning in 164 (27.3%) and benzodiazepine in 121 (20.2%). Other agents included household products in 42

(7.0%), rodenticide in 24 (4.0%), snake bite in 30 (5.0%), antidepressants or antipsychotics in 15 (2.5%), paracetamol in 8 (1.3%), kerosene in 5 (0.8%), various drugs in 5 (0.8%), copper sulphate in 4 (0.6%), methanol in 4 (0.6%) and corrosive agents in 3 (0.5%).

Figure 2: Intention of Poisoning among Study Patients (n=600)

With respect to intention, the majority of poisoning patients had a suicidal motive (397, 66.2%), as depicted in *Figure 2*. This was followed by stupefying (transport-related) poisoning in 164 (27.3%), accidental poisoning in 35 (5.8%) and homicidal poisoning in 4 (0.7%). Family disharmony was the predominant precipitating cause, identified in 376 (62.7%) cases, while 164 (27.3%) patients were victims of stupefying agents administered by others (*Figure 2*).

vomiting, present in 376 (62.7%) patients, followed by drowsiness in 334 (55.7%) and miosis in 183 (30.5%). Tachypnoea was recorded in 64 (10.7%) patients and tachycardia in 63 (10.5%). Abdominal pain was present in 92 (15.3%). Coma was documented in 27 (4.5%) patients and seizures were observed in 9 (1.5%). Notably, 76 (12.7%) patients had only a history of poisoning exposure without any objective clinical signs or symptoms at the time of presentation.

The clinical features observed at presentation are summarized in *Table III*. The most common symptoms were nausea or

Table III: Clinical Features of Poisoning Cases at Presentation (n=600)

Clinical Feature	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
No symptom/sign (history of poisoning only)	76	12.7
Nausea/Vomiting	376	62.7
Drowsiness	334	55.7
Miosis	183	30.5
Abdominal pain	92	15.3
Tachypnoea	64	10.7
Tachycardia	63	10.5
Increased sweating/salivation	48	8.0
Visual disturbance	25	4.2
Hypotension	25	4.2
Coma	27	4.5
Hypertension	18	3.0
Mydriasis	18	3.0
Dry skin/Dehydration	32	5.3
Muscle weakness	32	5.3
Bradycardia	17	2.8
Headache	15	2.5
Bradypnoea	13	2.2
Seizure	9	1.5

Figure 3: Outcome of Poisoning Cases and Cause of Death (n=600; deaths n=18)

The outcomes of the 600 study patients are presented in *Figure 3*. Nearly three-quarters of patients (426, 73.3%) recovered completely and were discharged with advice. A total of 130 (21.1%) patients left the hospital against medical advice (absconded), 26 (4.3%) were discharged on risk bond (DORB) and 18 (3.0%) patients died. Among the 18 deaths, 12 (66.6%) were due to pesticide poisoning, 3 (16.7%) due to benzodiazepine, antidepressant, or antipsychotic poisoning, 2 (11.1%) due to rodenticide and 1 (5.5%) due to snake bite. The agent-specific case fatality rates were: pesticide 6.86%, rodenticide 8.33%, snake bite 3.30% and benzodiazepine/antidepressant/antipsychotic 2.21%.

Table IV presents the association of sex with both the intention of poisoning and the type of poisoning agent. Female patients accounted for the majority of suicidal poisoning cases (220/397, 55.4%), whereas male patients predominated among those with accidental (23/35, 65.7%) and stupefying (160/164, 97.6%) poisoning. With respect to poisoning agent, travel-related poisoning was overwhelmingly male-predominant (160/164, 97.6%), while pesticide plus rodenticide poisoning was more common among females (112/199, 56.3%), as was benzodiazepine plus antidepressant poisoning (75/136, 55.1%). Snake bite was more frequent among males (18/30, 60.0%).

Table IV: Association of Sex with Poisoning Intention and Poisoning Agent (n=600)

Panel A: Sex and Intention of Poisoning						
Sex	Suicidal (n=397)	Homicidal (n=4)	Accidental (n=35)	Stupefying (n=164)	Total	p-value
Male	177 (44.6%)	1 (25.0%)	23 (65.7%)	160 (97.6%)	361	<0.001
Female	220 (55.4%)	3 (75.0%)	12 (34.3%)	4 (2.4%)	239	
Panel B: Sex and Poisoning Agent						
Sex	Pesticide + Rodenticide (n=199)	Travel-related (n=164)	Benzo-diazepine + Antidepressant (n=136)	Snake bite (n=30)	Others (n=71)	p-value
Male	87 (43.7%)	160 (97.6%)	61 (44.9%)	18 (60.0%)	35 (49.3%)	<0.001
Female	112 (56.3%)	4 (2.4%)	75 (55.1%)	12 (40.0%)	36 (50.7%)	

Figure 4: Association between Glasgow Coma Scale Score on Admission and Mortality (n=600)

The relationship between the GCS score at admission and patient mortality is illustrated in *Figure 4*. Among 42 patients admitted with a GCS score of 3 (fully unconscious), 7 (16.7%) died. Of 150 patients with a GCS of 4 to 10, 8 (5.3%) died. In the largest subgroup of 408 patients with a GCS of 11 to 15, only 3 (0.7%) died. This inverse relationship between admission GCS score and mortality was statistically significant, confirming that lower consciousness at the time of presentation was strongly associated with a higher risk of death in this cohort.

DISCUSSION

Acute poisoning constituted a substantial proportion of hospital admissions in the present study, accounting for 21.45% of total admissions in two adult medicine units of a tertiary care hospital. This proportion is considerably higher than that reported in earlier Bangladeshi studies and in developed countries, where poisoning accounts for approximately 10% of acute medical admissions [13]. The observed difference may reflect the urban tertiary care setting of the present study, where more severe or referred cases are concentrated, as well as evolving patterns of toxic exposure in Bangladesh.

The case fatality rate in this study was 3%, which is notably lower than previously reported figures from Bangladesh, such as 11.8% reported by Ahmed et al. and 7.06% by Rahman et al., as well as findings from South India [10,14,15]. This reduction in mortality may suggest a changing epidemiological trend toward ingestion of less toxic agents, particularly sedative-hypnotic drugs and household substances, in contrast to earlier dominance of highly toxic organophosphorus compounds. Additionally, improved supportive care and

earlier hospital presentation may have contributed to better outcomes.

The distribution of poisoning agents provides important insight into this transition. Although pesticides remained the most common agent (29.2%), a substantial proportion of cases involved travel-related poisoning (27.3%) and benzodiazepines (20.2%). The prominence of travel-related poisoning represents an emerging public health concern in Bangladesh, as also reported by Howlader et al., where victims are deliberately intoxicated during travel [11]. These cases were overwhelmingly male, reflecting gender-related exposure patterns and social mobility.

Demographically, poisoning predominantly affected young adults, with nearly 70% of cases occurring below 30 years of age and a mean age of 28.29 years. This finding is consistent with earlier studies conducted in Bangladesh by Ahmed et al. and Faiz et al., indicating that the economically productive and socially active age group is particularly vulnerable [10,12]. This pattern underscores the role of psychosocial stressors, including interpersonal conflicts, academic pressure and economic instability, in precipitating poisoning events.

Male predominance (60.2%) was observed overall, although females were more frequently associated with suicidal poisoning. This gender distribution differs from some regional studies but aligns with findings from Chittagong Medical College Hospital [16]. The higher proportion of male cases in the present study can be largely attributed to the inclusion of travel-related poisoning, which predominantly affects men. Conversely, female predominance in suicidal poisoning suggests underlying gender-specific psychosocial factors, including domestic stress and limited coping mechanisms.

Educational status appeared to influence the pattern of poisoning agents. Individuals with lower educational

attainment were more likely to use pesticides or rodenticides, whereas those with higher education more frequently used benzodiazepines and antidepressants. Similar observations were reported by Ahmed et al., suggesting that accessibility and awareness play significant roles in determining the choice of poison [10]. The higher use of psychotropic drugs among educated individuals may also reflect increased exposure to these medications and underlying mental health issues.

Occupational distribution revealed that students (31.1%) and housewives (24.5%) were the most affected groups. This finding is comparable to studies by Karki et al., where emotional vulnerability and social stressors were identified as key contributing factors [17]. Among students, academic failure and relationship issues may act as triggers, whereas among housewives, familial disharmony appears to be a dominant factor. Indeed, familial conflict was identified as the leading cause of poisoning in this study, accounting for approximately two-thirds of cases, consistent with findings by Eddleston et al. [13].

The majority of poisoning cases were intentional, with suicidal intent accounting for 66.2% of cases. This is in agreement with earlier reports from Bangladesh and other developing countries [12]. The relatively lower proportion of accidental poisoning may be attributed to the exclusion of pediatric cases, who are more prone to accidental exposures. The high prevalence of intentional poisoning highlights the need for mental health interventions and community-based support systems.

Clinically, the most common presenting features were nausea and vomiting (62.7%), drowsiness (55.7%) and miosis (30.5%). These findings reflect the predominance of pesticide and sedative drug poisoning and are consistent with established clinical patterns [10]. The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) on admission was found to be a strong predictor of outcome, with mortality decreasing markedly as GCS increased. Patients with a GCS score of 3 had a case fatality of 16.7%, compared to only 0.7% in those with scores between 11 and 15. This observation reinforces the prognostic value of GCS in acute poisoning, as also noted in other studies.

A notable finding was the delay in hospital presentation, with the majority of patients arriving between 5 and 8 hours after ingestion. Similar delays have been reported in other regional studies and may be due to lack of awareness, transportation barriers, or initial reliance on non-medical interventions [19]. Furthermore, more than 80% of patients did not receive any first aid prior to hospital admission, highlighting deficiencies in pre-hospital care and the need for community education.

Despite limitations in diagnostic facilities, particularly the absence of toxicological testing, the majority of patients (73.3%) recovered completely. However, pesticides remained the leading cause of death, accounting for two-thirds of fatalities, consistent with previous reports from Bangladesh and South Asia [15]. The higher case fatality associated with pesticides reflects their inherent toxicity and the challenges in management.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest a shifting pattern of poisoning in Bangladesh, characterized by increasing involvement of less toxic agents and emerging forms such as travel-related poisoning, alongside persistent challenges associated with pesticide exposure.

CONCLUSION

Acute poisoning represents a significant proportion of hospital admissions in Bangladesh, particularly among young adults. While pesticides remain the leading cause, there is a notable shift toward less toxic agents and emerging patterns

such as travel-related poisoning. The overall case fatality rate appears to be declining, possibly reflecting improved management and changing exposure profiles. Preventive strategies should focus on regulating access to toxic substances, strengthening mental health services, improving pre-hospital care and increasing public awareness.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study approved by the institutional ethical review committee.

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